

Sustainable Design: Strategies for Favouring Attachment between Users and Objects

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Abstract:

This paper explores the relationships between subjective experiences and objective design parameters. It presents findings from a research project that questions the notion of attachment between users and objects, attempts to understand its emotional origins and seeks to propose design strategies that favour its development. The researchers summarize the initial outcomes derived from ethnographic interviews conducted among thirty people.

This paper suggests that utility, appearance, symbolic meaning and users' experience are four key reasons that sustain the emotional attachment. Among them, users' experience seems to have the strongest and most durable effect on users' attachment to products. The study also reveals the importance of sentimental values which users associated with particular products, generated by relationships, memories, and life experiences. Four design strategies are proposed corresponding to each type of attachment. Sustainable design strategies informed by these insights and their implications for design practices are to be explored.

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1. Introduction

The current economic model still follows this rule: the more we produce and sell, the more the economics grow. As a result, tons of products end in landfills, even though they are still functional, thus causing great environmental impact. Ed Van Hinte (2004) suggests that people discard these objects possibly due to poor quality, out of boredom, outdated technology or simply because of a loss of attraction. Chapman (2005) argues that waste is symptomatic of failed user/object relationships, which leads to the act of discarding.

In order to gain a deeper understanding of how emotional attachment affects product longevity, the researchers conducted a brief literature review on the notion of attachment and emotion and on the nature of objects. Then, through in-depth interviews, the researchers sought to identify different types of attachment and develop design strategies corresponding to each type.

2. The Notion of Attachment and Emotion

2.1 Attachment— a borrowed concept

Attachment is originally a psychological term, which is defined as “an affectional tie that one person or animal forms between him/herself and another specific one [usually the parent] — a tie that binds them together in space and endures over time.” (Ainsworth, Bell and Stayton, 1974) According to Bowlby, a British developmental psychologist, notable for his pioneering work in attachment theory, the core of the term ‘affectional bond’ is the attraction one individual has for another (Bowlby, 1958/2005).

Current research on attachment, from the perspective of psychology, has been focused on the affectional bond between individuals. However, this affectional tie can also be found between users and objects, and is the focus of design for attachment. In the First International Conference on Design and Emotion, Cupchik (1999) suggests that profound attachment is largely built on an individual consciously or unconsciously relating to the sensory/ aesthetic, cognitive/ behavioural, and personal/ symbolic qualities of an object. Norman (2004) argues that the meaning of objects, emotional feeling and memory, are the main stimulants to product longevity. A survey conducted during the PRéco project (Racine and Lalande, 2003) found that users refrained from discarding objects to which they were attached, in spite of these being broken.

To conclude, Ainsworth’s six criteria for affectional bonds can be borrowed to describe the attributes of attachment between users and objects: being persistent, not transitory; involving a

particular person; involving an emotionally significant relationship; maintaining proximity; feeling sadness or distress at involuntary separation; seeking security and comfort in the relationship (Ainsworth, 1989).

2.2 Emotions underlying long term attachment

Among contemporary theories of emotion, many psychologists adopt the ABC model to define emotions: A. physiological arousal (e.g. heart rate changes), B. behavioural expression (e.g. facial expressions), and C. conscious experience, the subjective feeling of an emotion (Buck, 1985, 1988, 1999). Emotions are also categorized as primary and secondary. Primary emotions are those that we feel first (e.g. joy, pleasure), as a first response to a situation. Secondary emotions are feelings attached to objects, events, and situations through learning, which require additional input, based largely on memory (Plutchik, 1980). Primary and secondary emotions are two key elements which influence a person's behaviour. Chaudhuri (2006) argues that knowledge by acquaintance (emotion), known as subjective experience, is immediate and direct; knowledge by description (reason) is rational and indirect. According to him, rational beliefs are amenable to change; emotions are more resistant, fast, memorable and permanent.

Norman (2004) uses his tea pot collections to suggest three levels of emotion: the visceral, behavioural and reflective level. According to his theory, the visceral level is about appearance. The behavioural level is about experience with a product, based on function and performance. The reflective level is about consciousness, including the highest level of feelings, emotions and cognition. Esslinger, the founder of Frog Design, also believes emotion plays an important role in sustaining a long term attachment. He suggests that people will keep a product longer and take care of it if it has built in the emotional value (Demirbilek and Sener, 2003).

2.3 What do objects mean to users?

Consumption is seen as an individualistic process motivated by complex emotional drivers. Press and Cooper (2003) suggest that far more than the satisfaction of functional requirements, people today have a greater need for emotional, sensual and expressive experiences, in which goods and services play an essential part. Objects occupy significant portions of physical and symbolic space in our daily lives, but what do objects mean to users? A more socially and culturally rooted understanding of objects is imperative.

Boradkar (2006) suggests that objects are physical entities that are fashioned by human with symbolic and utilitarian value, that signify art as well as technology, that possess multiple and fluid meanings and that are at once ordinary and extraordinary. In this regard, objects have two traits, the physical substance and the symbolic meanings. Baudrillard, a French cultural theorist and philosopher, overlays Karl Marx's view of commodity systems and addresses three values of objects: use-value (utility), exchange-value (tradability) and symbol-sign value (Baudrillard, 1981). Chaudhuri (2006) categorizes objects into two: hedonic objects and utilitarian objects, relying on consumer's perceptions of objects. While the hedonic goods provide enjoyment, pleasure and fun, the utilitarian goods provide functional practicality. He suggests that the objects are considered to represent the consumer's needs, personality, lifestyle, and all the facets that make up the individual consumer. Norman further argues three aspects of objects, from the perspective of product design: its physical features, such as look, feel and sound; its performance, such as function, coherence and usability; and its message, such as cultural content and meaning (Norman, 2004).

3. Users' attachment to their objects

3.1 Overview of the interviews

In order to examine the attachment between users and objects, the researchers conducted interviews among thirty participants who were carefully selected in view of respecting a balance of gender, age, profession and background. Interview is one of the quantitative methods of ethnography, a methodology used to represent the perspective of everyday life. The researcher chose in-depth interview as the method and designed two sets of questions, consistent questions applied to all interviewees and spontaneous questions according to the conversation. Both the consistency and the personalization of the questions contributed significantly to analysis and synthesis of the responses.

The interview had three sections. Firstly, the participants were asked to describe their subjective experiences with an object to which they are particularly attached. Then, the researchers examined users' attitude and behaviour towards six categories of objects: transportation tools, IT/communication devices, entertainment products, domestic appliances, furniture and clothing and accessories. In the last section, eight objects were selected and inserted into various scenarios, each of which represents different design strategies to reinforce users' experience. The participants were asked to choose them in order according to the importance each object

meant to them. By analysing the outcomes of the interviews, the researchers proposed four types of attachment and analysed the underlying emotional reasons. These insights provide rich information for the researchers to develop design strategies for favouring attachment.

3.2 Four types of attachment

While being asked about the most attached object, with the exception of two interviewees who claimed not to be attached to anything, the majority of interviewees declared strong attachment to a specific object for various reasons. Therefore, the researchers analysed these reasons and propose four types of attachment.

- Attachment to the objects that perform well
- Attachment to the objects that satisfy the sense of aesthetics
- Attachment to the objects that reinforce self-esteem or public image
- Attachment to the objects that associate with experiences

3.2.1 Attachment to objects that perform well

This type of attachment is built on users' satisfaction with the level of functionality, utility and performance. These objects are considered reliable, trust-worthy, comfortable and practical; therefore, a strong bond is built. Some interviewees gave such stories as:

“I have a nail cutter that I have used for many years. It is not a beautiful one, but performs so well for me. Each time when I travel, I always make sure I have brought it with me. ”

“For some products, such as kitchen tools, I don't mind their look. As long as they work well, I will keep and use them for long time. But they have to work well on my way; even it may not be the way the products are designed for or suggested. ”

3.2.2 Attachment to objects that satisfy the sense of aesthetics

This type of attachment is built on users' appreciation of the aesthetic quality of objects, in terms of appearance, sensation, uniqueness, intelligence or artistic content. Users gain long term enjoyment and pleasure out of the aesthetic perception of objects, which can be either classical or evolving over time.

“I bought this wall clock in 1999...It is decorated with glass frames filled with dry grains, shells and flowers. Even now, I still think it is really beautiful... I don't think it will be outdated.”

“I have a pair of jeans that I wear for 15 years. When I first bought them, they were nice for the reason of looking skinny; then after five years, they were cool because they were so worn, and after ten years until now, they are still cool because they have holes.”

3.2.3 Attachment to objects that reinforce self-esteem or public image

This type of attachment is built on self-esteem or public image that objects reflect. The senses of confidence, proud and belonging are the emotions underlying this type of attachment.

“The object I have kept the longest is my coat. I like to keep it because I am very comfortable with it. Even it looks outdated. I feel it is me... I am happier to put on something I feel good in, instead of putting on something people think looks good on me.”

“People see you through the object you use. I bought this tablet PC three years ago. It makes me look professional when I communicate to people from other disciplines. When I talk to people and pull out my tablet PC, people take me much more serious. ”

3.2.4 Attachment to objects that associate with experience

This type of attachment is built on users' experiences, which are mostly associated with memories, relationships, life style and use experience. These objects are considered as part of users' lives.

“There's a sentimental value with the bike...When I was little, I didn't have friends, so I went biking. Therefore I really like my bike and go to many places with it... My bicycle even has a name; I call it 'Serpent'.”

“First I will say the kettle. It reminds me of the lifestyle that I am looking forward to. For me, it represents a peaceful tea time, a relaxing moment and a good mood. If one day I am rich, but don’t know how to enjoy the simple life, I will not feel happy. So the kettle is an attitude towards life and that’s important to me. ”

3.3 Attachment to six categories of objects

The researchers categorized everyday objects into six groups and selected typical products within each category. By analysing the participants’ attitude and behaviour to these objects, the researchers discovered the main reasons for broken attachment when the objects are discarded and for strong attachment when they are kept over time (see table 1).

Category	Representative objects	Main reasons for broken attachment	Main reasons for strong attachment
Transportation tools	Car, Bicycle	Cost of maintenance	Utility Driving/riding experience Lifestyle
IT/Communication devices	Mobile phone, Computer	Psychological and technological obsolescence (depreciation)	Utility Public image
Entertainment products	Television, DVD player, MP3 player, Game console	Technological obsolescence (depreciation)	Use experience
Domestic appliances	Kitchen appliances	Cost of repair and replacement	Utility Use experience
Furniture	In general	Moving	Monetary value Aesthetics Emotional experience (stable environment, sense of security and comfort)
Clothes and	In general	Psychological	Aesthetics

accessories		obsolescence	Self-esteem or public image
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Table 1: Main reasons for broken or strong attachment for each category of objects

3.4 Design strategies behind the eight scenarios

In the last section of the interview, subjects were shown images of eight objects with short descriptions of the scenarios in which they were placed. The design strategies were not revealed directly to the participants, but through the eight scenarios (see table 2). The participants were asked to choose them in order according to their preference or the importance each object meant to them. Then, the researchers analysed the design strategies that work efficiently and effectively in sustaining product longevity.

Proposed objects in eight scenarios		Represented strategies
Picture	Description	
	Chair - A self-made object made with recycled materials	Participatory design Responsible consumption
	iPod - A birthday gift from a spouse	Emotional design (relationship/gift), Aesthetic design
	Watch - A family heirloom	Emotional design (family bond) Aesthetic design Design for perceived value (antique),
	PDA - A digital device with leather case	Multifunction Upgradeability Aesthetic design (Sensation/texture/material)
	Shoes - A comfortable brand-named article	Brand loyalty Ergonomic design

	<p>Kettle</p> <p>- An Alessi designed piece, bought in a design exhibition</p>	<p>Aesthetic design</p> <p>Design for experience</p>
	<p>Bicycle</p> <p>- A long term travel partner</p>	<p>Design for experience</p> <p>Design for disassembly</p> <p>Emotional design (memory)</p>
	<p>Hockey stick</p> <p>- A souvenir of a winning match, signed by a famous player</p>	<p>Design for perceived value (collection),</p> <p>Emotional design (memory/pride)</p>

Table 2: Proposed objects and represented design strategies

The interviewees chose the eight objects in order and then scored them from 8 to 1 according to the order of preference. The final result was (see chart 1):

Chart 1: Order of eight objects according to users' preference

Through in-depth conversations, the researchers found that relationships, including family and friends, meant the most to users. The function of objects, reflected in practicality, utility and performance, is the second reason that affects product longevity. Following these two factors is the cost, relating to the monetary value of objects and the cost of replacement or repair. The research findings suggest that design strategies which are able to reinforce emotion, function, aesthetics and value could favour attachment. Among these design strategies, emotional design has the most influence on product longevity.

4. Design strategies for favouring attachment

The interviews provided rich insights into attachment, therefore, the researchers proposed four design strategies, each of which corresponds to one type of attachment. The application of these strategies is explored through successful design cases.

4.1 Design for adaptation

Design for adaptation is a strategy to design objects that are able to adapt to different contexts, such as user's needs, habits, ergonomic requirements, use environment, and the nature of the task, in order to reinforce users' satisfaction over time. This strategy corresponds to the type of attachment built on good performance. The long term satisfaction and trust, generated from the flexibility and reliability of objects, could favour attachment.

The latest Braun Pulsonic Shaver is a good example of design for adaptation. It combines shaving performance, ergonomic handling and aesthetic appeal altogether. The enhanced flexing head with the adaptation angle automatically navigates larger contours of the face, while the touch sensitive foils individually adapt to the slightest change in skin surface. Braun also offers a complete range of replacement parts according to users' needs. The high quality and flexibility prevent this product from being discarded rapidly.

Some existing design strategies can be used to achieve the goal of adaptation. Design for disassembly enables the parts of objects to be disassembled, replaced and modified. Modular design provides users multi-functionality with high flexibility. Ergonomic design and user interface design (UI) aim to optimize the utility of a product according to users' psychological and physiological needs. The design for adaptation strategy is suggested to apply in tool design, footwear design, furniture design, or in designing objects that are closely related to human body.

4.2 Design for expression

Design for expression is a strategy to design objects that satisfy users' sense of aesthetics through various communication means so that long term enjoyment is generated. It corresponds to the type of attachment that is built on the appreciation of aesthetics. Expression is a primary means of conveying social information among humans, a way to exchange ideas and emotions.

While human beings express their ideas and emotions by using language, facial expression and body posture, objects communicate through their “look” (appearance), “sense” (material and texture) or “intelligence” (content).

The Lagostina cookware is renowned for its design. Influenced deeply by architecture, philosophy and historical style, it combines the beauty of pure lines, with high-quality material and nice finishing. The aesthetics of this object is well expressed and communicated through its design vocabulary. Therefore, studying material culture and semiotic design are imperative for designers to broaden their means of expression. Learning from classical designs and other disciplines can also enrich design vocabulary. Design for expression strategy is suggested to apply in designing furniture, media objects (such as books), domestic appliances, or objects that provide decorative function.

4.3 Design for individuality

Design for individuality is a strategy to design objects that are important, unique and symbolic to the individual. It corresponds to the type of attachment that is built on self-esteem and public image. People are attached to the objects that can tell about who they are, what they do, and what kind of social group they belong. Design for individuality is a strategy to counter planned obsolescence by promoting the exercise of individual goals, desires and an individual's choices.

Customization allows consumers to create products according to their personal preferences. It has been widely applied in the car and furniture industries. As a process of encoding a product with symbolic meaning, symbolic design could prolong a product's lifespan because of the importance of the religious or cultural meanings to the individual. Strategies to create brand loyalty can also help to build a bond between users and objects at certain level. The design for individuality strategy is suggested to apply in designing clothes and accessories, and electronic products. Adding personal character to these products to strengthen the individual connection may prevent them from rapid obsolescence, caused by either outdated style or technologies.

4.4 Design for experience

Campbell (1987) suggests that what people seek is not the meaning of life, but the experience of being alive. As consumption is a natural way of experiencing unknown things, design for experience is a strategy to design objects that satisfy the desire of evoking fun, excitement,

success and many other emotions. It corresponds to the attachment that is built on users' experience, associated with memory, affection, relationship, life style and use experience.

The newly launched Nintendo Wii is a success story of design for experience. This experience-oriented product totally changes the image of video game consoles. It provides a more natural, intuitive and realistic feel. Players can use the Wii remote controller to mimic the real actions and reinforce user-experience, hence to bring fun and experience to everyone.

Jonathan Chapman (2005) suggests using low-tech narratives and fictions to enhance users' experience, bringing dreams and imagination to current busy and repetitive daily lives. Participatory design could strengthen the bond between users and objects through proactive involvement. Emotional design invokes users' memory and affections to gain a strong attachment. The design for experience strategy is suggested to apply in designing transportation tools and entertainment products. Users are encouraged to explore products, gaining fun and excitement out of unfolding them. The evolving experience could benefit product longevity.

5. Conclusion

Through literature review on the subject of attachment and emotion, two concepts derived from the field of psychology, and current research on sustainable design, the researchers suggest that there is a causal link between attachment and product longevity. The researchers gained some insights from the ethnographic interviews, conducted with thirty participants. The study suggests that utility, aesthetics, symbolic meaning and users' experience are four key reasons that sustain the emotional attachment between users and objects. Among them, users' experience seems to have the strongest and most durable effect on users' attachment to products. The study also reveals the importance of sentimental values which users associate with particular products, generated by relationships, memories, and life experiences. In the end, the researchers propose four design strategies: design for adaptation, design for expression, design for individuality and design for experience. A number of case studies are cited which demonstrate that these design strategies are applicable in product design, considering the objective of sustainable design. Currently, the authors are conducting research Metacycle (www.metacycle.ca), aimed at bringing discarded objects a second life by uniting designers and consumers within a virtual community dedicated to the application of these four design strategies. The experiment of applying these design strategies for favouring attachment in design practice will be the goal of future research.

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